

Motion of a Vortex between Parallel Walls

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Abstract

In this paper, motion of a vortex between parallel walls are investigated. Firstly, three laws of vortex motion are studied. Two-dimensional fluid motion, rectilinear vortices and motion of vortex filaments are expressed using complex variable methods. Consider the rectilinear vortices, motion of vortex filaments and pair of vortex filaments of in an incompressible inviscid liquid are analyzed. Finally, motion of a vortex between two parallel walls are discussed. It is found that The complex potential for the whole row can be written as

$$W = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log \tanh \frac{\pi z}{2a}. \text{ The motion of the vortex at the origin is remain at rest.}$$

1. Vorticity

If the motion of a fluid is described by a velocity vector field $\underline{v}(\underline{r}, t)$, then $\nabla \times \underline{v}$ is defined as the vorticity $\underline{\zeta}(\underline{r}, t)$, that is

$$\underline{\zeta}(\underline{r}, t) = \text{curl } \underline{v} = \nabla \times \underline{v}.$$

For two-dimensional motion, $\underline{\zeta} = \text{curl } \underline{v} = \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \hat{k}$.

1.2 Circulation

A scalar functional of considerable importance in the description of vortex flows is the circulation Γ around a simple closed curve C , defined as the line integral of the velocity.

$$\Gamma = \oint_C \underline{v} \cdot d\underline{s}. \quad (1)$$

We shall say that a curve is reducible if it can be shrunk continuously to a point without going outside the fluid. It follows from Stokes' theorem that the circulation around a reducible curve is equal to the flux of vorticity through an open surface A bounded by the curve, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma &= \oint_C \underline{v} \cdot d\underline{s} \\ &= \int_A \nabla \times \underline{v} \cdot \hat{n} \, dS \\ &= \int_A \underline{\zeta} \cdot \hat{n} \, dS. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Some convention is required for the sense in which the circulation is taken and the direction of the normal to the surface. We shall suppose that the relation is described by the right-hand-threaded screw.

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Equation (2) shows that, for arbitrary choices of contours and enclosed area A , if $\underline{\zeta} = \underline{0}$ then $\Gamma = 0$ and vice versa. Flow for which $\underline{\zeta} = \underline{0}$ is called irrotational, and flows for which this is not so are called rotational flows.

1.3 Vortex Lines and Vortex Tubes

In a region of fluid where the vorticity does not vanish identically, curves drawn parallel to the vorticity vector at each point of the curve are known as vortex lines. They are solution families of the differential equations

$$\frac{dx}{\xi} = \frac{dy}{\eta} = \frac{dz}{\zeta}, \text{ where } \xi, \eta, \zeta \text{ are components of } \underline{\zeta}.$$

The vortex lines passing through the points of a reducible curve define a cylindrical-like volume called a vortex tube. This term commonly implies that the cross-sections are small and oval, or even infinitesimal. The tube has the property that the vorticity is everywhere parallel to its surface, that is, $\underline{\zeta} \cdot \hat{n} = 0$ on the surface of a vortex tube. It follows that the flux of vorticity through any cross-section of the tube is constant, since if A_1 and A_2 are two cross-sections, the divergence theorem gives

$$\int_{A_1} \underline{\zeta} \cdot \hat{n} \, dS - \int_{A_2} \underline{\zeta} \cdot \hat{n} \, dS = \int_V \text{div } \underline{\zeta} \, dV = 0, \quad (3)$$

where V is the volume of the tube between A_1 and A_2 .

From the above equation between flux and circulation, the flux of vorticity along the tube is equal to the circulation round any closed curve on the tube wall which encloses the tube once. This quantity is called the strength of the tube and is the most natural measure of its intensity.

Figure. 1

1.4 Vorticity Equation

The equation of motion for an incompressible fluid can be written in terms of the vorticity, we have

$$\frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} - (\underline{v} \times \underline{\zeta}) = -\text{grad} \left(\frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{v^2}{2} + \Omega \right), \quad (4)$$

where the vorticity $\underline{\zeta} = \nabla \times \underline{v}$ and $\underline{F} = -\nabla \Omega$ is a conservative force. If the fluid has constant density, and taking the curl of both sides of (1.17), we have

$$\text{curl} \frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} - \text{curl}(\underline{v} \times \underline{\zeta}) = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\zeta}}{\partial t} - \underline{v} \text{div} \underline{\zeta} + \underline{\zeta} \text{div} \underline{v} - (\underline{\zeta} \cdot \nabla) \underline{v} + (\underline{v} \cdot \nabla) \underline{\zeta} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\zeta}}{\partial t} + (\underline{v} \cdot \nabla) \underline{\zeta} = (\underline{\zeta} \cdot \nabla) \underline{v},$$

$$\frac{D \underline{\zeta}}{D t} = (\underline{\zeta} \cdot \nabla) \underline{v}.$$

For two-dimensional motion

$$(\underline{\zeta} \cdot \nabla) \underline{v} = \zeta \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\hat{u} \hat{i} + \hat{v} \hat{j}) = 0,$$

and hence, we have

$$\frac{D \zeta}{D t} = 0.$$

1.5 Three laws of vortex motion

For the motion of an ideal barotropic fluid under the action of conservative external body forces, they can be expressed as following theorems:

- (i) Fluid particles originally free of vorticity remain free of vorticity.
- (ii) Fluid particles on a vortex line at any instant will be on a vortex line at all subsequent times. Alternatively, it can be said that vortex lines and tubes move with the fluid.
- (iii) The strength of a vortex tube does not vary with time during the motion of the fluid.

2. Two-Dimensional Motion and Complex Potential

As we have seen in Section 1.1, $\underline{v} = (u, v)$ in two-dimensional fluid motion. We shall suppose the fluid to be inviscid and take the fluid density, ρ , as constant, if in addition the motion is irrotational then the velocity potential, ϕ will exist and satisfy Laplace's equation, $\nabla^2 \phi = 0$.

For rotational or irrotational motion the continuity condition becomes

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \tag{5}$$

which is the condition that $v dx - u dy$ is a perfect differential of some function, ψ say.

Figure. 2

Therefore $d\psi = vdx - udy$, and we can write

$$\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} = v, \quad \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial y} = -u.$$

Consider the rate at which liquid mass crosses a curve AB, defined as the flow across AB. If $P(x, y)$ and $Q(x + \delta x, y + \delta y)$ are two neighbouring points on AB, PR and QR are parallel to the coordinate axes, then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{flow from right to left across PQ} &= \text{flow across PR} - \text{flow across QR} \\ &= \rho(v\delta x - u\delta y) = \rho\delta\psi. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore flow across AB from right to left $= \rho \int_A^B d\psi = \rho[\psi_B - \psi_A]$.

This property could be used as an alternative definition of ψ . It follows that if the flow across PQ is zero, PQ is along the line of flow or stream line at P and $d\psi = 0$.

Hence the stream lines are given by

$$\psi = \text{constant}, \quad (6)$$

and because of this fact ψ is called the stream function.

The stream function, ψ exists in this form only for two-dimensional motion and its existence depends on the density, ρ , being constant. Its existence does not depend on the motion being irrotational, as does existence of the velocity potential ϕ .

The components of the vorticity $\underline{\zeta}$ are $\left(0, 0, \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial y^2}\right)$. If the motion is irrotational,

ψ satisfies Laplace's equation $\nabla^2\psi = 0$ and we have from

$$\begin{aligned} u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} &= -\nabla\phi \\ &= -\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x}\hat{i} - \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y}\hat{j} \quad \text{with } \nabla^2\phi = 0, \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} &= -u = \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} &= -v = -\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

These are the Cauchy-Reimann conditions for $\phi + i\psi$ to be an analytical function of the complex variable $z = x + iy$ and so

$$\phi + i\psi = f(x + iy) = f(z),$$

where ϕ and ψ are called conjugate functions. We write

$$w = \phi + i\psi = f(z), \quad (8)$$

where w is called the complex potential for the motion.

We have consequently the complex velocity as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dw}{dz} &= \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} \\ &= \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial y} - i \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} \\ &= -u + iv. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Therefore the complex conjugate is

$$\frac{dw^*}{dz} = -u - iv$$

and hence

$$\frac{dw}{dz} \cdot \frac{dw^*}{dz} = u^2 + v^2 = |\underline{v}|^2.$$

2.1 Rectilinear vortices

Consider a straight circular vortex tube of radius a in an incompressible inviscid liquid in a direction perpendicular to the xy -plane. The motion will be two-dimensional. Suppose that the vorticity, $\underline{\zeta}$, perpendicular to the xy -plane is zero outside the tube and has a constant value ω inside. The circulation in every simple circuit surrounding the tube is $\pi a^2 \omega$, while in every circuit containing no point of the tube the circulation is zero. The liquid inside the tube is said to form a circular vortex, the strength of which is $\pi a^2 \omega = \kappa$.

By symmetry the vortex remains fixed in the fluid $\nabla^2 \psi = \zeta$ and using polar coordinates ψ is clearly a function of r only, therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \psi &= \frac{d^2\psi}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\psi}{dr} \\ &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{d\psi}{dr} \right) \\ &= \begin{cases} \omega & \text{for } r < a \\ 0 & \text{for } r > a. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$r \frac{d\psi}{dr} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \omega r^2 + A & r < a \\ B & r > a. \end{cases}$$

$$\psi = \begin{cases} A \ln r + \frac{1}{4} \omega r^2 + C, & r < a \\ B \ln r + D & r > a. \end{cases}$$

Since ψ is finite at the origin, we must have $A = 0$. Both ψ and the velocity $\frac{d\psi}{dr}$ will be continuous at $r = a$, therefore we have

$$C + \frac{1}{4} \omega a^2 = B \ln a + D$$

and
$$\frac{1}{2} \omega a = \frac{B}{a},$$

so
$$B = \frac{1}{2} \omega a^2,$$

$$C = D + \frac{1}{2} \omega a^2 \ln a - \frac{1}{4} \omega a^2,$$

ψ is determinate to the extent of an arbitrary constant D , which we shall take as zero. Writing the strength as $\kappa = \pi a^2 \omega$, we have

$$\psi = \frac{\kappa}{4\pi a^2} (r^2 - a^2) + \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \ln a, \quad r < a$$

$$\psi = \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \ln r, \quad r > a.$$

Outside the vortex, the motion is irrotational, therefore ϕ exists and is given by the conjugate function

$$\phi = -\frac{\kappa\theta}{2\pi}.$$

Hence the complex potential is

$$\begin{aligned} w &= \frac{-\kappa\theta}{2\pi} + \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln r \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} (\ln r + i\theta) \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln z \quad \text{for } |z| > a. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

If $a \rightarrow 0$ and $\omega \rightarrow \infty$ in such a way that κ remains constant, we obtain a rectilinear or columnar vortex filament, often referred to simply as a vortex. The complex potential at every

point in the liquid is then given by $w = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln z$. If the vortex filament is at the point z_0 , the complex potential is clearly

$$w = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln(z - z_0). \tag{11}$$

2.2 Single vortex filament

Figure. 3

Take a vortex filament of strength κ at the point $A(z_0)$. Then $w = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln(z - z_0)$. The velocity at the point $P(z)$, is therefore given by

$$-u + iv = \frac{dw}{dz} = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi(z - z_0)} = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi R e^{i\theta}},$$

where $R = AP$ and $\arg(z - z_0) = \theta$. Thus $-u - iv = \frac{-\kappa e^{i(\theta + \frac{\pi}{2})}}{2\pi R}$.

Thus the direction of motion at P is at right angles to AP with speed $\frac{\kappa}{2\pi R}$ in the sense given by the rotation of the vortex at A .

2.3 Motion of vortex filaments

A circular vortex alone in the fluid possesses no tendency to set itself in motion and the same therefore applies to a vortex filament. If there are several vortex filaments, the motion of the filament at the point P is the same as the motion which would be produced at P by the remaining vortices if the vortex at P did not exist. It must be observed, however, that the complete motion of the fluid may be due not only to vortices but also to the presence of sources, streams, or other causes.

Thus if w is the complex potential of a flow which contains a vortex of strength κ at the point z_0 , the complex velocity of the vortex is

$$-u_0 + iv_0 = \left\{ \frac{d}{dz} w - \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln(z - z_0) \right\}_{z=z_0}.$$

2.4 Pair of vortex filaments

Suppose there are vortex filaments of strengths κ and κ' at A and B respectively. Then the centre G of the system, which remains fixed, divides AB in the ratio of $\kappa' : \kappa$. A moves with velocity $\frac{\kappa'}{2\pi AB}$ perpendicular to AB and B moves in the opposite direction with velocity

$\frac{\kappa}{2\pi AB}$, AB thus rotates about G with angular velocity $\frac{(\kappa + \kappa')}{2\pi AB^2}$.

Figure. 4

If the vortices are of equal and opposite strength, $\kappa' = -\kappa$, G is at infinity and both A and B will have a velocity $\frac{\kappa}{2\pi AB}$ perpendicular to AB, therefore they move in parallel paths through the liquid with this velocity. Such an arrangement is called a vortex pair. If the vortices are at points z_1 and z_2 the complex potential is

$$w = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{z - z_1}{z - z_2} \right),$$

and the stream function

$$\psi = \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \ln \frac{r_1}{r_2},$$

where $r_1 = |z - z_1|$, $r_2 = |z - z_2|$. The stream lines are

$$\frac{r_1}{r_2} = \text{constant}, \quad (12)$$

which form a set of coaxial circles with A and B as limiting points. The motion is not steady and the stream lines are not fixed but move through the liquid along with the vortices.

There is no flow across the plane bisecting AB at right angles, therefore this could be made a rigid barrier and the liquid on one side removed without altering the motion of that on the other.

2.5 Vortex in Quadrant

Suppose there is a vortex, strength κ , at $A(r, \theta)$ in liquid bounded by two walls at right angles to each other; taking these as coordinate axes, the image of A in Oy in an equal and opposite vortex $-\kappa$ at $B(r, \pi - \theta)$.

Figure. 5

Therefore if liquid occupied whole of the upper half of the z -plane with the addition of B , the motion in the first quadrant would remain unaltered. The image system for A and B in Ox is vortices $-\kappa$ and κ at $D(r, -\theta)$ and $C(r, \pi + \theta)$ respectively. The vortices to the left of Oy are the image of those to the right.

The velocity of A is the resultant of the velocities produced by B , C and D . Its radial velocity

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{r} &= \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{AD} - \frac{\sin \theta}{AB} \right) \\ &= \frac{\kappa}{4\pi r} (\cot \theta - \tan \theta) \\ &= \frac{\kappa}{2\pi r} \cot 2\theta. \end{aligned}$$

The transverse velocity

$$r \dot{\theta} = \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{AC} - \frac{\cos \theta}{AB} - \frac{\sin \theta}{AD} \right) = -\frac{\kappa}{4\pi r}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\dot{r}}{r\dot{\theta}} &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{dr}{d\theta} = -2 \cot 2\theta, \\ \ln r &= \ln C - \ln \sin 2\theta \end{aligned}$$

and the equation of the path is $r \sin 2\theta = C$,

where C is the constant of integration. This curve is known as Cotes Spiral. Squaring and substituting for x and y in terms of r and θ , its Cartesian equation is

$$\frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{y^2} = \frac{4}{C^2}$$

thus it has the lines $x = \frac{1}{2}C$, $y = \frac{1}{2}C$ as asymptotes. The vortex will ultimately move parallel to the x axis with speed $\frac{\kappa}{2\pi}$.

3. Motion of a Vortex between Parallel Walls

Suppose there is a vortex of strength κ in liquid in midway between parallel walls a distance “a” apart. Choosing the origin at the vortex and the x-axis parallel to the walls then the image of the vortex in the walls $y = \frac{1}{2}a$ $y = -\frac{1}{2}a$ are vortices κ at ia and $-\kappa$ at $-ia$ respectively.

These vortices will have vortex images of strength κ in the opposite walls $y = \frac{1}{2}a$ $y = -\frac{1}{2}a$ at $-2ia$, $2ia$ respectively, and so on producing a similar system of images in optical case. The images system is therefore a row vortices along the y-axis each a distance ‘a’ apart, alternating in sign. We have vortices

$$\kappa \text{ at } 0, \pm 2ia, \pm 4ia, \dots, \pm 2nia, \dots$$

$$-\kappa \text{ at } \pm ia, \pm 3ia, \dots, \pm(2n-1)ia, \dots$$

The complex potential for vortex κ at origin is $w_1 = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log z$.

The complex potential for vortex κ at $\pm 2nia$ is

$$\begin{aligned} w_p &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z - 2nia) + \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z + 2nia) \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z + 4n^2a^2) \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{4n^2a^2}\right), \end{aligned}$$

neglecting the constant term.

The complex potential for vortex $-\kappa$ at $\pm(2n-1)ia$ is

$$\begin{aligned} w_q &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z - (2n-1)ia) + \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z + (2n-1)ia) \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log(z^2 + (2n-1)^2a^2). \\ w_q &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{4(2n-1)^2a^2}\right), \text{ neglecting the constant term.} \end{aligned}$$

The complex potential for the whole row can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 w &= w_1 + w_p + w_q \\
 w &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log \frac{z \prod \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{4n^2 a^2} \right)}{\prod \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{(2n-1)^2 a^2} \right)} \\
 &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log \frac{\sinh \frac{\pi z}{2a}}{\cosh \frac{\pi z}{2a}} \\
 &= \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log \tanh \frac{\pi z}{2a}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The motion of the vortex at the origin is $\left(\frac{dw_0}{dz} \right)_{z=0}$, where $w_0 = w - \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \log z$.

Figure. 6

We have
$$\frac{dw_0}{dz} = \frac{i\kappa}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\pi}{a} \operatorname{cosech} \frac{\pi z}{a} - \frac{1}{z} \right),$$

which is zero at the origin. Hence the vortex remain at rest. The stream function

$$\begin{aligned}\psi &= \frac{i\kappa}{4\pi} \log \left[\tanh \frac{\pi}{2a} (x + iy) \tanh \frac{\pi}{2a} (x - iy) \right] \\ &= \frac{i\kappa}{4\pi} \log \frac{\cosh \left(\frac{\pi x}{a} \right) - \cos \left(\frac{\pi y}{a} \right)}{\cosh \left(\frac{\pi x}{a} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{\pi y}{a} \right)}\end{aligned}$$

The streamlines are given by $\cosh \left(\frac{\pi x}{a} \right) = A \cos \left(\frac{\pi y}{a} \right)$, where A is real constant; there are ovals symmetrical about the axis as shown in figure 7.

Figure. 7

Conclusion

A circular vortex alone in the fluid possesses no tendency to set itself in motion and the same therefore applies to a vortex filament. The complete motion of the fluid may be due not only to vortices but also to the presence of sources, streams, or other causes.

If the vortices are of equal and opposite strength, G is at infinity and both vortices will have the same velocity perpendicular to axis, therefore they move in parallel paths through the liquid with this velocity.

If a vortex of strength κ in liquid in midway between parallel walls a distance “ a ” apart. Choosing the origin at the vortex and the x -axis parallel to the walls then the image of the vortex in the walls $y = \frac{1}{2}a$ $y = -\frac{1}{2}a$ are vortices κ at ia and $-\kappa$ $-ia$ respectively. The vortex at the origin is remain at rest.

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